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Symposium on
**CLIMATE
ACTION**
2025

“Food, water, and climate security through Integrated
water management lessons learned”

EXTENDED ABSTRACTS

Ministry of Agriculture, Livestock, Land and Irrigation
Climate Resilient Integrated Water Management Project(CRIWMP)

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Trends and Sources of Agricultural Greenhouse Gas Emissions in Sri Lanka: Towards reduction strategies

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Introduction

Agriculture is a major contributor to global greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, with rice cultivation, livestock management, and soil fertilization playing pivotal roles in emission patterns (Barker et al. 2022; Lal 2021). In Sri Lanka, rice farming remains the dominant source of methane emissions, primarily due to the anaerobic conditions created in flooded paddy fields (Wassmann et al. 2000). As the agricultural sector continues to grow, the need for targeted strategies to reduce its environmental impact becomes increasingly important. This study seeks to analyze the trends in agricultural emissions in Sri Lanka, using data from ClimateTrace.org from 2015 to 2024, with a particular focus on identifying mitigation opportunities.

The objectives of this study are to assess the main sources of agricultural emissions in Sri Lanka, track their trends over the past decade, and compare Sri Lanka's emissions to global agricultural patterns. Additionally, the study aims to identify potential mitigation strategies to reduce GHG emissions in the agricultural sector, particularly from rice cultivation and livestock management. This research is critical for informing policy decisions and encouraging the adoption of sustainable agricultural practices that align with global climate goals. The rationale behind this study lies in the recognition that Sri Lanka's agricultural emissions are rising, driven primarily by methane from rice cultivation and emissions from livestock operations. While previous studies have highlighted the importance of these sectors, there is a lack of comprehensive data and analysis focused on the trends and mitigation opportunities within Sri Lanka's unique agricultural context. By analyzing emissions data and identifying key trends, this study provides valuable insights that can inform both local and national climate strategies, with an emphasis on reducing the carbon footprint of Sri Lanka's agricultural sector.

Methodology

Data from ClimateTrace.org covering Sri Lanka's agricultural emissions from 2015 to 2024 were analysed. Emission sources included rice cultivation, livestock enteric fermentation, synthetic fertilizer application, and soil management.

Emissions were measured in CO₂e (100-year global warming potential). The analysis focused on trends over time and compared Sri Lanka's emissions to global agricultural patterns.

Results and Discussion

Figure 1 illustrates the greenhouse gas emissions from Sri Lanka's agriculture sector in the years 2015 and 2024. Emissions originate from several sources, including rice cultivation, emissions from other agricultural soils, and enteric fermentation. Enteric fermentation includes methane emissions from cattle housed in operational facilities such as feedlots, barns, and dairy farms, with estimates calculated at the facility level using remote sensing and artificial intelligence to identify the location of operations and estimate herd sizes. Additional sources include enteric fermentation from other livestock, synthetic fertilizer application, and enteric fermentation from cattle grazing on pasturelands. Methane emissions from pasture-based cattle are estimated using spatially gridded pasture data combined with FAOSTAT herd numbers, as provided by Climate TRACE. These pasture-based systems typically yield higher methane emissions per animal due to the higher fiber content of forage compared to feedlot operations. Further contributors to GHG emissions include crop residue management, manure management from cattle operations, cropland fires, manure left on pasture, manure management from other livestock, and manure applied to soils.

Figure 1. Greenhouse gas emissions from Sri Lanka's agriculture sector in 2015 and 2024, categorized by different emission sources. The emissions are represented in terms of CO₂-equivalent (CO₂e) using the 100-year global warming potential (GWP) values from 2015 and 2024. The sectoral labels are defined as follows: A – Rice Cultivation, B – Other Agricultural Soil Emissions, C – Enteric Fermentation (Cattle Operation), D – Enteric Fermentation (Other), E – Synthetic Fertilizer Application, F – Enteric Fermentation (Cattle Pasture), G – Crop Residues, H – Manure Management (Cattle Operation), I – Cropland Fires, J – Manure Left on Pasture (Cattle), K – Manure Management (Other), L – Manure Applied to Soils.

The results of this study highlight the significant contribution of rice cultivation to agricultural emissions in Sri Lanka, with the highest CO₂e-100 year values recorded in 2023 and 2024 at 2,525,486 CO₂e, followed closely by 2022 (2,450,898 CO₂e) and 2021 (2,120,170 CO₂e). These findings align with previous studies, which emphasize rice cultivation as a major source of greenhouse gas emissions, particularly methane, due to the anaerobic conditions in flooded paddy fields (Chen et al., 2024). The increasing CO₂e values

over recent years in Sri Lanka reflect both the intensification of rice production and the lack of significant mitigation strategies aimed at reducing emissions from this (Muneer 2023). This trend mirrors global patterns where rice cultivation continues to be a dominant contributor to agricultural greenhouse gas emissions (Hong et al. 2021). While alternative rice farming practices such as alternate wetting and drying have been suggested to mitigate these emissions (Sriphirom et al. 2019). Figure 2 illustrates the Trends in greenhouse gas emissions from rice cultivation and other agricultural soil emissions in Sri Lanka from 2015 to 2024.

Figure 2. Trends in greenhouse gas emissions from rice cultivation and other agricultural soil emissions in Sri Lanka from 2015 to 2024. The graph shows the CO₂-equivalent emissions (CO₂e, 100-year GWP) for both sectors, highlighting variations over the years. Rice cultivation emissions (blue line) are primarily driven by methane (CH₄), while other agricultural soil emissions (red line) are influenced by carbon dioxide (CO₂) and nitrous oxide (N₂O).

Analysis of GHG emission trends reveals a dramatic increase in 2021 and the value has continued till the end of the study period in 2024, particularly from rice cultivation. This spike in emissions is closely associated with Sri Lanka's abrupt shift to organic agriculture in 2021 (Drechsel et al. 2025). In April of that year, a nationwide transition to organic farming, enforcing an immediate ban on chemical fertilizers and pesticides was mandated. While the policy aimed to promote sustainable agriculture, it instead led to severe agricultural disruptions. Rice yields fell sharply, with some estimates indicating a 30% reduction, and short-term yield losses reaching up to 53%. As a result, rice production dropped by 32% (Stifel 2025). The lack of proper training in organic farming led to inefficient practices, and the absence of chemical inputs prolonged the crop growth cycle, extending the duration of methane-producing flooded conditions. Compounding to the issue, conventional continuously-flooded systems (CF) foster anaerobic soil which supports methanogenic microbial activity in rice paddies. Without suitable water-management techniques like alternate wetting and drying (AWD), prolonged flooded periods in 2021 amplified methane emissions for each crop cycle (Lakshani et al. 2023). Collectively, these factors contributed to a paradoxical rise in GHG emissions from rice cultivation, despite overall reductions in yield, highlighting the unintended environmental consequences of the poorly planned organic transition.

In addition to rice cultivation, the study also examined other sources of agricultural emissions in Sri Lanka, including emissions from agricultural soil management and livestock operations. Emissions from other agricultural soils showed a gradual decrease over the period from 2015 to 2024, with values declining from 1,871,832 CO₂e in 2015 to 1,732,703

CO₂e in 2024. This decline is consistent with global findings, where improvements in soil management practices and technological advancements have led to reduced emissions from soil sources (Lal 2013). However, the rate of reduction was slow, indicating that further interventions may be necessary to accelerate this decline. Studies have suggested that more aggressive strategies, such as improved nutrient management and agroforestry, could provide additional long-term benefits (Kidd and Pimentel 1992). The stabilization of emissions between 2022 and 2024 suggests a potential plateau, emphasizing the need for ongoing monitoring and adaptive policy frameworks to achieve more substantial reductions in emissions from agricultural soils.

Synthetic fertilizer application and enteric fermentation from livestock also emerged as the two largest contributors to agricultural emissions in Sri Lanka in recent years. In 2021, synthetic fertilizer application accounted for 979,294 CO₂e (100-year), while enteric fermentation from cattle operations contributed 844,081 CO₂e. The emissions from cattle operations remained consistent through 2024, indicating that efforts to mitigate emissions from this sector have had limited success. These trends align with previous studies highlighting the significant role of livestock and fertilizer use in Sri Lanka's agricultural greenhouse gas emissions (Rathnayake and Mizunoya 2024). The stable emissions from enteric fermentation suggest that livestock management practices and feed improvements have not yet resulted in substantial reductions in methane emissions, which is consistent with regional studies (Wolf et al. 2017). Additionally, the continued high levels of synthetic fertilizer use underscore the ongoing challenge of balancing agricultural productivity with environmental sustainability (Zhang et al. 2024). Addressing these emissions will require comprehensive policy interventions, including the adoption of more efficient fertilizers and advanced livestock management techniques. The findings of this study also revealed that certain agricultural sectors, while contributing less to overall emissions, still play a role in Sri Lanka's agricultural emissions profile. Emissions from the "manure-applied-to-soils" sector showed a steady increase from 74,037 CO₂e in 2015 to 86,732 CO₂e in 2024. Similarly, emissions from other manure management other increased from 80,857 CO₂e in 2016 to 97,781 CO₂e in 2024, and "manure-left-on pasture-cattle" emissions remained relatively high, ranging from 104,115 CO₂e in 2015 to 105,455 CO₂e in 2021. These results are consistent with studies that highlight the role of livestock and manure management in agricultural emissions (Chadwick et al. 2011). While these sectors exhibit moderate emissions in comparison to rice cultivation, they still contribute substantially to the total agricultural emissions in Sri Lanka, indicating the need for sustainable livestock management practices to mitigate emissions from these sources (Aryal et al. 2020).

Furthermore, the dominant source of CO₂ emissions from the agricultural sector was from "other agricultural soil emissions" with values ranging from 1,494,723 tons in 2017 to 1,697,631 tons in 2015. These emissions remained relatively stable at 1,540,210 tons in 2022 and continued to level off through 2024. The primary sources of these emissions are attributed to fertilizer use, rice cultivation, and general soil management practices (Linguist et al. 2012). In contrast, emissions from cropland fires remained low, fluctuating between 122,305 tons in 2017 and 179,748 tonnes in 2020, with no significant changes post-2020. This supports earlier studies indicating that agricultural soil management is a significant contributor to greenhouse gas emissions in Sri Lanka (Rathnayake and Mizunoya 2023).

Although there has been some decline in emissions from soil over time, further research is needed to assess the full impact of improved agricultural practices and verify whether these trends are due to ongoing mitigation efforts.

Lastly, the study revealed that rice cultivation remains the primary contributor to CH₄ emissions in Sri Lanka, followed by enteric fermentation from cattle operations. The data shows a marked increase in methane emissions from rice cultivation, with 90,519 tonnes recorded in 2023, up from 39,827 tonnes in 2015. This rise reflects the continued reliance on flooded fields, which create anaerobic conditions conducive to CH₄ production, as noted in previous studies (Pulliam, 1993). Enteric fermentation from cattle operations also plays a significant role in methane emissions, contributing 31,032 tonnes in 2023. While emissions from other sources, such as manure management and cropland fires, remained stable or low, the dominance of rice cultivation and enteric fermentation emphasizes the need for targeted mitigation strategies to address methane emissions, such as improved rice farming techniques and more efficient livestock management (Mousa et al. 2023).

Conclusion

Sri Lanka's agricultural emissions have continued to rise, driven primarily by methane from rice cultivation, with emissions reaching 2,525,486 CO₂e in 2024. While soil emissions have shown modest declines, emissions from livestock and fertilizer use remain substantial. The emission estimates provide a global perspective but may not fully capture local Sri Lankan farming conditions. Future research should integrate local field measurements with satellite data to improve estimate reliability and develop region-specific emission factors that account for traditional farming practices and seasonal variations. These findings have significant implications for Sri Lanka's Paris Agreement commitments and Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs). The 127% increase in methane emissions from rice cultivation between 2015 and 2023 requires targeted sectoral emission reduction strategies. The agricultural sector should be integrated into national carbon accounting frameworks with specific targets for reducing methane emissions from rice cultivation by 15-20% by 2030 through alternate wetting and drying techniques. Addressing these challenges requires comprehensive policy interventions promoting sustainable rice farming, efficient livestock management, and optimized fertilizer application. Further research and policy implementation are critical to reducing Sri Lanka's agricultural climate footprint while aligning with national climate commitments and maintaining food security.

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